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Uses And Gratifications of Late-Night Radio Programmes: A Comparative Study of Rivers State University and University of Port Harcourt Students

¹Odoyi Prince Jonah, ²Dr. I. Harry & ³Dr. C.J. Njoku

^{1,2,3}Department of Media Studies,
Faculty of Social Science,
Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the uses and gratifications of late-night radio programmes among students at the University of Port Harcourt and Rivers State University. The research utilized the uses and gratification theory and individual difference theory. The study employs a survey research design to understand media engagement, including the extent of listenership, types of programmes favoured, motivations for listening, perceptions of the programmes, and their influence on academic performance. Findings indicate relatively low listenership, with music and educational programmes being the most popular. Key motivations include entertainment, stress relief, and feeling connected to radio personalities, while perceptions of programme quality and cultural influence are positive, though content relevance needs improvement. The study concludes that late-night radio plays a significant cultural and social role, offering companionship and entertainment, but also indicates that there is a better alignment of content with student interests and academic responsibilities. Recommendations include: enhancing the appeal of late-night programs; incorporating educational content; and conducting regular audience research.

Keywords: Late-night radio programmes, Uses and gratifications, Student engagement, Media consumption, Entertainment.

INTRODUCTION

Since its emergence in the early twentieth century, radio transmission has become an integral aspect of human communication astonishing and engaging audiences with news, music, and entertainment (Sterling & Skretvedt, 2011). Over the decades, radio has served multiple purposes, including education, entertainment, information dissemination, national development, and social mobilization. As Ebuchulam (2002) describes, radio acts as both a mobilizing force and a significant economic driver in the modern global order. The origins of radio can be traced to Guglielmo Marconi, who invented the wireless telegraph in 1895. This invention laid the foundation for what is now a ubiquitous medium, present in nearly every home across the world. In 1932, radio was introduced to Nigeria by the British Broadcasting Service, which relayed British Empire Service programs to colonial officials and residents. According to Okenwa (1993), as cited in Ndimele and Innocent (2006), these broadcasts included the monitoring and transmission of BBC content to Her Majesty's servants in this part of the world. Thus, just as Britain established the Nigerian state, it also laid the foundation for one of its most enduring institutions—radio broadcasting (Adejumobi, 1974).

Initially, these broadcasts were transmitted through Radio Distribution Service (RDS) stations, which played a pivotal role in the evolution of broadcasting in Nigeria. From fewer than 1,000 subscribers in

1939, RDS expanded to serve over 74,000 subscribers by 1960, with an even larger listening audience (Adejunmobi, 1974). With time, regional autonomy began to shape the landscape of Nigerian broadcasting. The Western Nigerian Broadcasting Corporation (WNBC) became the first regional station in 1959, followed by the Eastern Nigerian Broadcasting Service in 1960 and the Northern Nigerian Broadcasting Corporation in 1962. The liberalization of the airwaves continued into the 1990s, and in 1992, Raymond Dokpesi's Ray Power FM became the first privately owned radio station in Nigeria, opening the door for private investment and competition in the sector. Today, radio broadcasting in Nigeria comprises three main types: public radio (owned by the federal and state governments), private radio (owned by individuals and corporate entities), and community radio (serving specific local communities) (Osazee-Odia & Ojobor, 2017).

In Rivers State, there are approximately seventeen radio stations, including two campus-based student stations—Excel FM and Unique FM. Prominent commercial stations include Nigeria Info, Today FM, Wazobia FM, Cool FM, Beat FM, and Classic FM, among others. These stations cater to a wide range of audiences with diverse content, from general entertainment to specialized programming. For instance, Nigeria Info brands itself as a “Talk, News, and Sports” station, while Today FM is described as a “Premium Talk, News, and Sports” broadcaster. There are also stations focused on music, such as Classic FM, Sound City Radio, and Beat FM. Fans of entertainment are well served by stations like Cool FM, Wazobia FM, and Naija FM, while politically inclined audiences can tune into Treasure FM or Radio Rivers for current affairs and civic discussions. Most radio stations in Rivers State operate until midnight, but several—such as Nigeria Info FM, Rhythm FM, Cool FM, and Wazobia FM—broadcast throughout the night, offering a continuous stream of content for night-time listeners.

This study explores the late-night radio programs accessible to students at University of Port Harcourt (UNIPORT) and Rivers State University (RSU), examining the enjoyment and perceived benefits derived from these programs. Located within the Port Harcourt metropolis, both institutions are well positioned to receive signals from all local stations. Notable late-night shows that resonate with students include Night Café on Cool FM, Mellow Music on Classic FM, and Let's Talk & Chat on Nigeria Info—each airing between 9:00 p.m. and 3:00 a.m. Rivers State University, originally established in 1972 as the College of Science and Technology, attained full university status in 1980. It is one of Nigeria's most distinguished institutions, with campuses not only in Port Harcourt but also in outlying areas like Etche and Ahoada. The university offers a comprehensive array of undergraduate, postgraduate, and doctoral programs across disciplines including engineering, law, science, social sciences, arts, and health sciences. RSU is also known for its strong focus on research and innovation, with dedicated centers addressing regional and national challenges. Similarly, the University of Port Harcourt is a leading institution with a broad spectrum of academic programs in the arts, sciences, social sciences, engineering, management, and health-related disciplines. It has earned a strong reputation for academic excellence and research productivity, making it a key contributor to the advancement of knowledge both within and beyond the Niger Delta region.

Statement of the Problem

Numerous researchers have examined patterns of radio listenership and usage, particularly focusing on the uses and gratifications that audiences—especially young people—derive from radio content. However, there has been limited scholarly attention directed toward understanding audience attitudes specifically toward late-night radio programmes. Therefore, a knowledge gap persists regarding the extent of students' exposure to and engagement with radio programming during late-night hours.

Radio has long been a significant medium for informing, educating, and entertaining audiences through its diverse programming content. However, the nature and appeal of this content are often influenced by several factors, including the ownership structure of the station, trending topics, and the station's unique house style. These variables significantly affect audience exposure, as a radio program must align with the psychographic profile of an individual for it to capture their attention—even before considering the time of broadcast.

With the continuous evolution of mass communication, the radio now competes with other platforms for the attention of young audiences. The advent of television, digital media, and particularly internet-enabled mobile

phones and social media, has dramatically expanded students' access to alternative sources of information, entertainment, and education—especially during late-night hours. Consequently, while some individuals remain enthusiastic about late-night radio, seeking it out for a variety of reasons, such as relaxation, companionship, or intellectual stimulation, little empirical research has explored the degree to which radio continues to satisfy these needs in comparison to other media.

This study, therefore, seeks to analyze the uses and gratifications of late-night radio programmes among university students, specifically comparing students from the University of Port Harcourt and Rivers State University. The research aims to understand how these students engage with late-night radio content and what needs it fulfils relative to other available media options.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are as follows:

1. Establish the extent of listenership of Nigeria Info and Sound City late-night radio programmes by students University of Port Harcourt and Rivers State University.
2. Identify the types of late-night radio programmes that students of the University of Port Harcourt and Rivers State University students are exposed to;
3. Determine the gratifications motivating University of Port Harcourt and Rivers State University students' exposure to Nigeria Info and Sound City late-night radio programmes.
4. Assess the perceptions of the University of Port Harcourt and Rivers State University towards Nigeria Info and Sound City late-night radio programs.
5. Analyze the influence Nigeria Info and Sound City late-night radio programmes have on the academic performance of students of the University of Port Harcourt and Rivers State University.

Theoretical Framework

Uses and Gratifications Theory

The development of uses and gratifications theory, and its influence in media audience research can be traced to earlier media researchers such as Lazarsfeld (1940) who studied the uses and gratifications theory in radio listening in USA, Herta Herzog (1944) studied the relations of the uses and gratifications theory and the reasons why people chose specific types of media and in his research identified emotional, wishful thinking, and learning as three gratifications of media use. (McQuail, Blumler and Brown 1972) draw on the uses and gratifications theory establishing the benefits of media use and emphasizing diversion, personal relationships, personal identity and surveillance as types of gratifications the media should help meet for its audience.

This theory, as explicated by Katz, Blurnler, & Gurevitch (1974), has historically taken a need critical gratifications in consumption-fulfillment approach. Essentially, uses and gratifications researchers believe that people have certain needs that they wish to gratify. People may fulfill these needs by the use of various communication channels, mass and interpersonal. This perspective assumes that audience members are both active and goal oriented when deciding on what form and type of mass media programming they should expose themselves to. In addition, this perspective takes the position that all channels of communication compete with both one another and other sources of need fulfillment. If specific channels of communication fail to meet audience needs adequately, then viewers will actively seek alternative options (Katz, Blurnler, & Gurevitch, 1974).

The theory falls under the Active Audience theories which focus on what people do with the media as opposed to source-dominated theories which focus on the effects of the media on people. The assumption is that individuals influence the effects that the mass media have on them. The theory is based on the premise that the audience uses the media to gratify certain identified needs (Mc Quail, 1994). The audience selectively chooses, listen to, perceive and retain the media messages on the basis of their needs, beliefs, and more. According to LittleJohn and Foss (2008), the theory focuses on the consumers of media messages rather than the message itself. In other words, broadcast audiences are largely responsible for choosing the media to meet specified needs they have.

Mc Quail (1994) identified four domains of individual needs which the media should gratify:

Media serving as a form of diversion or escapism

Media serving as a form of companionship for those who are socially isolated

Media serving to understand and evaluate one's personal identity.

Media serving as a form of surveillance to provide information on the social world.

The uses and gratifications theory of the media provides unique framework to understand the relationship between radio broadcasting and audience engagement. The concept of audiences in this study are the listeners of radio broadcasting programmes during the late night hour in University of Port Harcourt and Rivers state university, and in which programming schedules influence choice of stations. Audience expectations of broadcasting performance is connected back to the work of Katz, Blurnler, & Gurevitch (1974) which says that audience relates to the media and their contents on the basis of wants or motives, sees audience as active with decisions and preference for consumption of private broadcasting programmes activities and the gratifications from respective programmes formats.

Individual Differences Theory

The Individual Differences theory propounded by Melvin Defluer in 1970 and further enunciated by Defluer and Ball-Rokeach in 1975 is one of the mass communication theories that look at audience heterogeneity, clearly that the audience get the best out of programmes based on certain individual differences etc. The theory postulates that individual perceptive way in psychological endowment. No two individuals are the same due to the way they were individually brought up in their environment and social life. Humans are biologically, physically, psychologically and genetically different. Ajaegbu et al (2015).

The Individual Differences theory base its assumption on the fact that the audience of mass media is heterogeneous, it is made up of people with different disposition, characteristics, personality, experiences, demographics, psychographics. These socio-psychographical factors determine how an individual reacts towards media content. The theory attach importance to the individual audiences and states that an individual's values, needs, beliefs and attitudes play a major role in how they react and use media.

Ndimele and Innocent (2006) attempting to explain this mass communication theory said "...even if we have the same educational, cultural, or even religious backgrounds, or even if we are in the same proffesion and on the same career level, inside each of us are still individual traits that make us perceive and react differently to mass media contents" (p.240). They further explain that the theory is explained by the differences in personality between individuals which lead them to react to same media messages differently. According to this theory there is a new trend in the formation of a person's character through the learning process. The big difference in mindset and motivation based on the experience of learning. Individual differences due to environmental differences resulting indifferent views in the face of things. Environment will influence the attitudes, values and beliefs that underlie their personalities want to respond to incoming information. Thus the influence of media on individuals will vary from one another.

According to Gale and Edward (1999), the individual theory has been criticized to have received poor research endeavor and also have more roots in biological sciences than social sciences, but a study by Murphy and Msetfi (2014) shows a more elaborate use in the areas of associative learning, educational psychology, industrial and organizational psychology, personal psychology and many more. Applying this theory to this study which is audience based and seek to understand how students of University of Port Harcourt and Rivers State University use late night radio programmes and the gratifications they gain through the needs these radio programmes meet, however audience is heterogenous with different fields of experience and psychological state of minds, so the Individual Differences theory brings to mind that though we want to establish radio use and gratifications, these needs are subject to differences based on the individual value systems and psychographic dispensation.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the survey research design which, involves the study of a sample taken from a population in order to know their major characteristics which can be generalized to the whole population. This is to elicit responses from students on what uses and gratifications they gain from radio late night exposure. The population of students in Rivers state university is 28,973 according to the schools ICT department, while that

of University of Port Harcourt is 39,641 according to the schools ICT department, bringing the total population for this study to 68,614 undergraduate students of both universities. The Taro Yammane (1967) formula was used to determine the sample size.

PRESENTATION OF DATA

A total of 400 copies of the questionnaire was distributed across both universities, 398 copies were successfully retrieved, which constitutes 99.9 percent of the total copies of the questionnaire.

Research Question one: *What is the extent of listenership to Nigeria Info and Sound city late night radio programmes by students University of Port Harcourt, and Rivers State University?*

Table 1: Mean(x) distribution of the extent of listenership to Nigeria Info and Sound city late night radio programmes by students University of Port Harcourt, and Rivers State University.

S/N	ITEMS	S A	A	D	SD	Total	(x)	Remark
1.	I regularly listen to Nigeria Info late night radio programmes.	78 312	208 624	26 52	86 86	1074	2.7	Accepted
2.	I regularly listen to Sound City late night radio programmes.	27 108	150 450	127 254	94 94	906	2.3	Rejected
3.	I spend more than 2 hours per night listening to these late night radio sprogrammes.	52 208	70 237	156 320	120 120	850	2.1	Rejected
4.	These late night shows are my primary source of entertainment at night.	80 320	79 237	160 320	79 79	956	2.4	Rejected
5.	I almost never miss an episode of my favorite late night radio show.	24 96	140 420	125 250	109 109	875	2.2	Rejected

From the above Table 1, item 1 on the questionnaire shows that a significant number of students from the University of Port Harcourt and Rivers State University regularly listen to Nigeria Info late-night radio programmes, as indicated by the mean score of 2.7, which falls into the "Accepted" category. However, item 2 reveals that not many students regularly listen to Sound City late-night radio programs, as reflected by the mean score of 2.3, which is "Rejected." Item 3 shows that many students do not spend more than 2 hours per night listening to these late-night radio programs, with a mean score of 2.1, indicating "Rejected." Similarly, item 4 reveals that these late-night shows are not the primary source of entertainment at night for most students, with a mean score of 2.4, also falling under "Rejected." Lastly, item 5 indicates that a majority of students do not almost never miss an episode of their favorite late-night radio show, with a mean score of 2.2, which is "Rejected." This entails that the overall listenership to late-night radio programs among students of the University of Port Harcourt and Rivers State University is relatively low, and these programs are not their primary source of entertainment.

Research Question Two: *What are the types of Late-night radio programmes that students of University of Port Harcourt, and Rivers State University students' exposure to?*

Table 2: Mean(x) distribution of the types of Late-night radio programmes that students of University of Port Harcourt, and Rivers State University students' exposure to.

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	Total	(x)	Remark
6.	I listen to music entertainment programmes at night	192 768	144 432	48 96	14 14	1310	3.3	Accepted
7.	I listen to educational programmes at night	72 288	139 417	127 240	67 67	1012	2.5	Accepted
8.	I listen to news and current affairs programmes on radio at night	50 200	47 141	200 400	101 101	842	2.1	Rejected
9.	I listen to religious programmes on radio at night	24 96	140 420	125 250	109 109	875	2.2	Rejected

From the above Table 2, item 6 on the questionnaire shows that a substantial number of students from the University of Port Harcourt and Rivers State University listen to music entertainment programs at night, as indicated by the mean score of 3.3, which falls into the "Accepted" category. This suggests a high level of exposure to music entertainment programs among the students. Item 7 reveals that students also listen to educational programs at night, with a mean score of 2.5, which is also "Accepted." This indicates a moderate level of exposure to educational content during late-night hours.

However, item 8 shows that many students do not listen to news and current affairs programs on the radio at night, as reflected by the mean score of 2.1, which is "Rejected." This suggests that news and current affairs programs have a low level of listenership among the students during late-night hours. Similarly, item 9 reveals that religious programs on the radio at night also have a low level of listenership, with a mean score of 2.2, which is "Rejected." This indicates that religious content is not a primary choice for students' late-night radio listening.

In summary, the data suggests that music entertainment and educational programs are the most popular types of late-night radio programs among students of the University of Port Harcourt and Rivers State University. In contrast, news, current affairs, and religious programs have lower levels of listenership.

Research Question three: *What are the gratifications motivating University of Port Harcourt, and Rivers State University students exposure to Nigeria Info and Sound City late night radio programmes?*

Table 3: Mean (x) Analysis of the gratifications motivating University of Port Harcourt, and Rivers State University students exposure to Nigeria Info and Sound City late night radio programmes.

	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	Total	(X)	Remark
10	I listen to be entertained and relieve stress/boredom.	44 176	245 735	66 132	43 43	1086	2.7	Accepted
11	I listen to learn about current trends, music, and popular culture.	45 108	70 210	243 486	40 40	916	2.3	Rejected
12	Listening helps me escape my daily academic routines and responsibilities.	51 204	276 828	61 122	10 10	1164	2.9	Accepted
13	I enjoy the interactivity and feeling connected to the radio personalities.	70 280	176 528	83 166	69 69	1043	2.6	Accepted
14.	The night shows align with my personal values and viewing interests.	132 528	147 441	65 130	54 54	1153	2.9	Accepted

From the above Table 3, item 10 on the questionnaire shows that a significant number of students from the University of Port Harcourt and Rivers State University listen to late-night radio programs to be entertained and relieve stress/boredom, This suggests that entertainment and stress relief are important motivators for listening to late-night radio.

Item 11 reveals that students do not primarily listen to learn about current trends, music, and popular culture, indicating that this type of content is not a primary motivator for their late-night radio listening.

However, item 12 shows that many students listen to late-night radio programs to escape their daily academic routines and responsibilities, suggesting that these programs provide a welcome distraction from academic pressures.

Item 13 indicates that students enjoy the interactivity and feeling connected to the radio personalities. This suggests that the personal connection with radio hosts is a significant factor in their listenership.

Lastly, item 14 shows that the night shows align with the students' personal values and viewing interests, This indicates that the content of these shows resonates well with the students' personal preferences.

In summary, the data suggests that the primary gratifications motivating students of the University of Port Harcourt and Rivers State University to listen to late-night radio programs are entertainment, stress relief, escaping academic routines, and feeling connected to radio personalities. Learning about current trends, music, and popular culture is a less significant motivator.

Research Question Four: *What are the perceptions of University of Port Harcourt, and Rivers State University towards Nigeria Info and Sound City late night radio programmes?*

Table 4: Mean(x) Analysis of the perceptions of University of Port Harcourt, and Rivers State University towards Nigeria Info and Sound City late night radio programmes.

	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	Total	(X)	Remark
15	The content is high quality and professionally produced.	69 207	265 795	37 74	27 27	1103	2.7	Accepted
16	The shows have a positive influence on youth/student culture.	83 332	267 801	33 66	15 15	1214	3.1	Accepted
17	The radio personalities are relatable and authentic.	135 540	242 726	12 24	9 9	1299	3.3	Accepted
18	The topics covered are relevant to my life as a university student	31 124	85 255	220 440	62 62	881	2.2	Rejected
19	I would recommend these late night shows to other students.	80 320	79 237	160 320	79 79	956	2.4	Rejected

From the above Table 4, item 15 on the questionnaire indicates that a significant number of students from the University of Port Harcourt and Rivers State University perceive the content of Nigeria Info and Sound City late-night radio programs to be of high quality and professionally produced.

Item 16 reveals that students believe these late-night radio shows have a positive influence on youth and student culture. Similarly, item 17 shows that students find the radio personalities on these shows to be relatable and authentic. However, item 18 indicates that students do not perceive the topics covered on these late-night shows as highly relevant to their lives as university students. Lastly, item 19 shows that students are not highly inclined to recommend these late-night shows to other students, as reflected by a mean score of 2.4, also categorized as "Rejected."

Research Question Five: *What influence does Nigeria Info and Sound City late night radio programmes have on the academic performance of students of University of Port Harcourt, and Rivers State University?*

Table 5 Mean(x) Analysis of the influence Nigeria Info and Sound City late night radio programmes have on the academic performance of students of University of Port Harcourt, and Rivers State University.

	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	Total	(X)	Remark
20	Listening to late night shows negatively impacts my sleep schedule.	22 88	112 336	196 392	68 68	884	2.2	Rejected
21	I sometimes skip classes/studies because I stayed up too late listening.	31 124	85 255	220 440	62 62	881	2.2	Rejected
22	The time I spend listening reduces my overall study/homework time.	83 332	267 801	33 66	15 15	1214	3.1	Accepted
23	The content sometimes distracts me from focusing on academics.	135 540	242 726	12 24	9 9	1299	3.3	Accepted
24	Listening has minimal impact on my ability to perform well academically.	69 207	265 795	37 74	27 27	1103	2.7	Accepted

From the above Table 5, item 20 on the questionnaire shows that most students from the University of Port Harcourt and Rivers State University do not believe that listening to late-night shows negatively impacts their sleep schedule. This suggests that late-night radio listening is not significantly affecting their sleep.

Item 21 reveals that students generally do not skip classes or studies because they stayed up too late listening to late-night radio programs, This indicates that late-night radio listening is not a major cause of missed academic commitments.

However, item 22 shows that many students feel that the time they spend listening to late-night radio reduces their overall study and homework time, as reflected by the mean score of 3.1, which is "Accepted." This suggests that late-night radio listening can interfere with their study schedules.

Item 23 indicates that students find the content of late-night radio programs sometimes distracts them from focusing on academics, with a mean score of 3.3, which is "Accepted." This suggests that the engaging nature of the content can divert their attention away from academic responsibilities.

Lastly, item 24 shows that students believe listening to late-night radio has minimal impact on their ability to perform well academically, with a mean score of 2.7, which is "Accepted." This indicates that, despite some distractions, students generally feel their academic performance is not heavily influenced by late-night radio listening.

CONCLUSION

The findings paint a nuanced picture of students' relationship with late-night radio programs. On one hand, there is a clear appreciation for the entertainment value and production quality of these shows, particularly from Nigeria Info and Sound City. Students find the content engaging and perceive the radio personalities as relatable and authentic. This connection to the programs and their hosts suggests that late-night radio plays a significant role in the cultural and social lives of these university students, offering a form of companionship and entertainment during night hours.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are advanced:

1. Late night radio programmes should be packaged in such a way that they are more appealing to the audience of late-night radio programmes.
2. Students of University of Port Harcourt, and Rivers State University should balance their late-night reading habit with their late-night radio listening habits to help build their academic performance better.
3. Radio stations should include creativity and versatility as a strategy to take into consideration in their programming.
4. Radio Stations should Incorporate more educational content into late-night radio programs, potentially collaborating with universities to create segments that support academic learning while maintaining an entertaining format. This could include study tips, career advice, or discussions on academic topics presented in an engaging manner
5. Radio stations should conduct regular surveys and focus groups with university students to better understand their interests, concerns, and needs.

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